

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300
Sacramento, CA 95814

In Reply Refer to:
2025-01349639-S7-001

October 17, 2025

Michael Strauss
Environmental Division Chief
Military Ocean Terminal Concord
Department of the Army
Military Surface Deployment and Distribution Command
834th Transportation Battalion
410 Norman Avenue
Concord, CA 94520-1142

Subject: Reinitiation of Informal Consultation for the General Repair of the T-4/T-7
Bridges included in the General Bridges, Roads, and Utilities Project at Military
Ocean Terminal Concord (MOTCO), Contra Costa County, California

Dear Michael Strauss:

This letter is in response to the Department of the Army's (Army) August 12, 2025, letter requesting reinitiation of informal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed General Repair of the T-4/T-7 Bridges included in the General Bridges, Roads, and Utilities Project (proposed project) at Military Ocean Terminal Concord (MOTCO) in Contra Costa County, California. Your request letter was received via electronic mail (email) by the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office on August 12, 2025. The Army determined that alterations to the original proposed project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) (SMHM). The Army also determined that the proposed project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the endangered San Francisco Bay-Delta distinct population segment (DPS) of the longfin smelt (longfin smelt DPS; *Spirinchus thaleichthys*). All other determinations for listed species in the previous consultation remain the same. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following: (1) the Army's August 12, 2025, request for reinitiation of consultation letter; (2) the September 30, 2025 revision of the August 2025, *Biological Assessment – Reinitiation Package U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service*

Military Ocean Terminal Concord (MOTCO), T-4/T-7 Bridges included in the General Bridges, Roads, and Utilities Project Contra Costa County, CA (BA); (3) email and telephone conversations between August 2025 and September 2025; and (4) and other information available to the Service.

Add:

The Service concurs with the Army's determination that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the endangered longfin smelt DPS. Due to the small scope and nature of the project and avoidance measures for this species, the Service anticipates that adverse effects to the longfin smelt DPS are unlikely to occur. The Service anticipates that longfin smelt DPS are not likely to be present in the channel during installation of the coffer dam and will be isolated from the project area once the coffer dam is in place. Any longfin smelt that swim into the channel will be able to evade and avoid the equipment and crews by swimming back into the larger open waters of the Suisun Bay and any adverse effects from the proposed project will likely be insignificant and discountable.

The remainder of this document represents the Service's biological opinion for the SMHM.

Add:

CONSULTATION HISTORY

May 5, 2016	The Service issued a concurrence letter for informal consultation to the Army on the federally endangered soft bird's-beak (<i>Chloropyron molle</i> ssp. <i>molle</i>), the threatened delta smelt (<i>Hypomesus transpacificus</i>) and its designated critical habitat, the endangered California clapper rail (<i>Rallus longirostris obsoletus</i>), the endangered California least tern (<i>Sternula antillarum browni</i>), and the endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (<i>Reithrodontomys raviventris</i>) for the project (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2016-I-0226).
August 12, 2025	The U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) Military Programs and Installation Environmental Support Section emailed the Service requesting reinitiation of consultation for the Army.
September 29, 2025	The Service reviewed the request and responded to the Corps that the current habitat conditions in the project area had changed from what was described in the 2016 informal consultation and that adverse effects to SMHM are likely to occur. The Service held a telephone conversation with the Corps and the Corps agreed to send a revised BA with a change in their determination for the SMHM.

September 30, 2025

The Corps sent a revised BA with the change in their determination that the proposed project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the SMHM.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Add to the Description of the Proposed Action:

Although specific changes to the proposed project are not “remove and replace with” actions for this reinitiation amendment, the Service is adding changes to the proposed project to the *Description of the Proposed Action* in this section for comparison to the original proposed project from 2016.

Pile Repair. The original project description proposed repairs of up to 33 deteriorated piles. Based on recent inspection reports, the anticipated number of piles requiring repair has changed to 29 piles. Sections of deteriorated timber piles will be cut at the footing and below the cap, removed, and replaced with new sections of timber piling that have been treated with a waterborne preservative (ammoniacal copper arsenate, ammoniacal copper zinc arsenate, or chromated copper arsenate per the American Wood Protection Association Standard A2). The extent of the deterioration is not confirmed in 4 piles and may require deeper excavation to complete repairs. Timber pile removal and installation will be achieved through use of a small land-based crane on top of the deck. Please refer to the BA for specifics on pile number and position.

Steel Splice Sleeve Installation. Steel splice sleeves will be installed approximately two and a half feet into the mudline on all piles requiring removal and repair (maximum of 29 piles). Water insensitive epoxy with the consistency of putty will be applied on holes of the jacket for uniformity.

Pile Backfill. Proposed design changes include pouring controlled low-strength material (CLSM), a self-consolidating, cementing material, around timber piles to backfill to the existing level of native surrounding substrate after necessary repairs are completed. Although steel sleeves were described for the cut-and-post repair, CLSM was not part of the previous design description. The CLSM is necessary to assist in protecting the timber pile during low tides and provide structural support. If excavation deeper than 3 feet occurs, it is anticipated to be backfilled with CLSM.

Cofferdam. The original design proposed temporary dewatering of the Project Area through installation of an inflatable cofferdam to complete the timber pile repairs. The original design proposed cofferdam installation at 10 locations with each cofferdam measuring approximately 800 square feet. The proposed period of use was eight days but could be up to two weeks. Design updates have remained consistent with the proposal to utilize cofferdams during construction; however, cofferdam size, number of installation disturbances during construction, and required timeframe for use have changed as outlined below.

To reduce multiple disturbances during construction, only two cofferdam installations are proposed encompassing an area of approximately 16,100 and 25,000 square feet for T4 and T7

respectively. The cofferdams will be installed along the entire length of the bridge and have supporting wings that extend upward to the beginning of the road (Figure 1). Installation of the cofferdam will occur during periods of low tide when little to no water is anticipated to be within the area to be enclosed. Any remaining water will be discharged into the ocean downstream in a controlled manner using BMPs such as dewatering bags to filter sediments. The proposed timeframe for cofferdam use will be 44-47 days. All in-water work, including cofferdam installation and removal, will occur between August 1 and January 31.

Land-Based Crane. Repair work will be conducted with a land-based crane located on the bridge abutment. The land-based crane will be utilized to hoist the steel sleeves and piles while workers are completing activities on the mud line. All debris and damaged piles would be carefully lifted from the water and disposed of at an approved and permitted facility appropriate for disposal of creosote-treated piles.

Timber Mats and Shoring. The proposed design refinements also include timber mats and shoring to support the bridge from collapsing during construction. The shoring will be raised to provide sufficient space to remove the cutoff piles and treat the interface with wood preservative.

Temporary Access and Construction Schedule. Vehicle access to Bridges T-4 and T-7 will be through Guard Gates 2 and 5 and will follow Port Chicago Highway to White Road. Temporary foot access by construction crews is anticipated within the vegetation immediately adjacent to the bridges associated with work at and below the mudline. The designated construction staging area is located away from waterways, and comprised of paved surfaces, concrete pads, and previously disturbed vegetated areas. This area will be used for temporary storage of equipment and supplies, including short-term placement of asphalt millings and base materials. Construction activities are scheduled to occur in one construction season. As feasible, construction work will occur during daylight. If nighttime work cannot be avoided, lighting will be directed to the work area, minimizing the lighting of tidal marsh habitat. In-water work will be completed between August 1 and January 31. Any additional elements of the Project may take place during the rainy season with implementation of approved Best Management Practices and specifications to work in inclement weather.

Figure 1.

Updated Conservation Measures for SMHM:

1. A Service-approved biologist will be present during all project-related ground disturbances or vegetation removal. This includes the initial disturbance and any subsequent work necessary for maintenance of clear space. The Service-approved biologist will conduct surveys for SMHM and their nests, and other listed species prior to vegetation removal/cutting activities and will also monitor during the work.
2. Where marsh vegetation representing potentially suitable habitat for SMHM is present and needs to be removed, work will be conducted using motorized hand-held tools, such as a gas or electric-powered hedge trimmer, in a manner that enables and encourages wildlife to escape from the construction area. Handheld powered tools are acceptable, as long as the blades are within guards, and there are no rotating strings or blades. Vegetation will be trimmed to a canopy height of 3-4 inches (which appears to be the lowest commonly used by SMHM), in a way that allows for a “pathway” that can be used by the equipment, cofferdam, and foot traffic. When pickleweed is trimmed, caution will be taken to not disturb the root base of the plants as much as feasible.

3. A Service-approved biologist will conduct pre-construction surveys for presence of SMHM and their nests in the areas where equipment will need to drive or people will need to walk, and the biologist will slowly walk ahead of the equipment to reduce risk of take and help encourage flushing of mice. When traversing through the SMHM habitat, the equipment and cofferdam cleared pathway will be utilized exclusively but may be expanded with oversight from the Service-approved biologist.
4. The Service-approved biologist will conduct daily surveys for SMHM immediately prior to and during all construction activities (i.e., immediately prior to ground disturbance). The Service-approved biologist will be present during all project-related ground disturbances. This includes the initial disturbance, vegetation trimming, and any subsequent work necessary for maintenance of clear space. If a SMHM or any mouse that the biologist or construction personnel believe may be this species is encountered, all work that could result in direct injury, disturbance, or harassment of the individual animal will immediately cease, and the Contracting Officer and Service-approved biologist will be immediately notified. The Service-approved biologist will monitor the animal(s) until they determine that it is not imperiled by predators or other dangers. Following any encounters with a potential SMHM during construction, the Service-approved biologist will notify MOTCO Environmental and the Service via email and telephone within one working day.
5. In the unanticipated event that any contractor, employee, or Army personnel discover or inadvertently kill or injure a SMHM, they will immediately report the incident to the Service-approved biologist. The Service-approved biologist will contact MOTCO Environmental and the Service to report the dead or injured animal via electronic mail and telephone within one working day.
6. All equipment will be stored only at designated staging areas located on previously disturbed or developed areas that are devoid of vegetation. This includes pipes, storage containers, landscaping materials, plastic sheeting, or other materials that small animals could use for cover. No materials or supplies that could potentially entrap mice will be stored in salt marsh vegetation. This includes pipes, storage containers, landscaping materials, plastic sheeting, netting, or other materials that small animals could use for cover. All equipment will be stored at designated staging areas, which consists of existing disturbed or developed areas that are devoid of vegetation. No plastic monofilament netting will be used as it poses an entanglement hazard for the SMHM and other small animals.

Add Action Area:

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” MOTCO is in the east San Francisco Bay region, approximately 10 miles inland past the Carquinez Strait, which connects Suisun Bay to San Pablo Bay. The proposed project is located along Kinney Boulevard, east of Port Chicago on MOTCO south of Pier 2. For the purposes of the effects assessment, the Action Area for this reinitiation encompasses approximately 0.75 acre.

Add:**ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK for the JEOPARDY DETERMINATION**

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the range wide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current range wide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action but that are not part of the action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Add Status of the Species:*Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse*

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*), both of which are listed as endangered. Information about the salt marsh harvest mouse biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species’ range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/species_nonpublish/3643.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species’ listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

Add Environmental Baseline:

Environmental baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The environmental baseline includes the past and present

impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

MOTCO is a United States Army Military Surface Deployment and Distribution Command munitions and general cargo trans-shipment facility. All the upland areas within the Action Area can be categorized as developed, ruderal, and landscaped. Developed areas primarily consist of paved and compacted access roads, structures, or disturbed roadsides. Roadsides consist of ruderal (“weedy”) vegetation, and bare ground is present in patches. These areas have been disturbed by human activities and are dominated by nonnative annual grasses and other ruderal species. The Action Area is a matrix of fresh and saline emergent wetland, tidal marsh, and coastal scrub and receives ample tidal flow dominated by saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*), pickleweed (*Salicornia pacifica*), rushes (*Juncus* spp.), and spearscale (*Atriplex prostrata*). South of the proposed project site is primarily ruderal terrestrial environments interspersed between the developed military roadways.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The Action Area includes approximately 0.6 acre of tidal salt marsh habitat that is within the over 500 combined acres of tidal salt marsh habitat surrounding the Action Area. Recent surveys completed by WRA Environmental Consultants (WRA 2022), indicate that all major marsh areas under MOTCO jurisdiction support salt marsh harvest mouse, even areas that have a relatively lower pickleweed cover. The areas around T4 and T7 are both mapped as areas with low to moderately low potential for occurrence (between 10 and 30%). It is reasonable to assume that the SMHM occur within the Action Area.

Add:

Previous Consultations Within or Adjacent to the Action Area

MOTCO has consulted numerous times within their boundaries but this section only describes consultations within and adjacent to this proposed project’s Action Area.

MOTCO prepared a ground squirrel management plan in 2012 which was the subject of a section 7 consultation between the Army and the Service. The Service concurred in a letter dated May 3, 2012, with the Army’s determination that the Ground Squirrel Management Plan for MOTCO may affect, but would not likely adversely affect the California tiger salamander central valley distinct population segment, California red-legged frog (CRLF), SMHM, California Ridgway’s rail (CRR), or soft bird’s-beak (Service File Number: 08ESMF00-2012-I-0186). Updates to the management plan were completed in 2021 with minimal changes that the Army determined did not require reinitiation.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Remediation of the Department of the Army's Military Ocean Terminal, Concord's Sites 32 and 33 Project (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-

2013-F-0029) on February 21, 2014, with an amendment issued (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2013-F-0029-R001) on September 25, 2015, to the Army on the effects of the project on the delta smelt and its critical habitat, the SMHM, the CRR, and soft bird's-beak.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Military Ocean Terminal Concord Military Munitions Response Program Remedial Investigation and Feasibility Study (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2013-F-0040) on April 15, 2014, to the Army for effects of the project on the SMHM, the CRR, and soft bird's-beak.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Modernization and Repair of Piers 2 and 3 at Military Ocean Terminal Concord (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2014-F-0002-5) on February 4, 2015, to the Army for effects of the project on the delta smelt and its critical habitat, the SMHM, the CRR, the CRLF, and soft bird's-beak.

The Service issued an informal concurrence letter for the General Repairs of Bridges, Roads, and Utilities at Military Ocean Terminal Concord Project (Service File Number 08FBDT00-2016-I-0226) on May 5, 2017, to the Army on the effects of the project on the SMHM, the CRR, the California least tern, and soft bird's-beak.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Proposed Maintenance Dredging at Military Ocean Terminal Concord Project (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2020-F-0010) on December 30, 2019, to the Army with a reinitiation issued (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2020-F-0010-R001) on December 13, 2021, for effects to the delta smelt and its critical habitat, and the SMHM.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Routine Maintenance and Repair Activities on Military Ocean Terminal Concord (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2020-F-0018) on June 22, 2020, to the Army for effects of the project on the delta smelt and the SMHM.

The Service issued a programmatic biological opinion for the Department of the Army's Military Ocean Terminal Concord Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan, Programs, and Projects for 2023-2028 (Service File Number: 2022-0070999-S7-001) on November 5, 2024, to the Army for the effects of the project on the SMHM and CRR.

The Service issued a biological opinion for the Department of the Army's Groundwater Monitoring Well Replacement Project at Military Ocean Terminal Concord (Service File Number: 2025-0021104-S7-001) on April 10, 2025, to the Army for effects to SMHM.

Add: Effects of the Proposed Action

Effects of the action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

SMHM have the potential to be within the immediate construction footprint of the proposed project and within the considerably larger expanse of high quality habitat that surrounds the proposed project site. The tidal marsh habitats within the Action Area likely support the SMHM. The proposed project will likely generate temporary noise and visual disturbance from personnel and construction equipment. Equipment noise, vibration, and visual disturbance may interfere with the normal behaviors of SMHM if present in the project area or immediately nearby. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, reproducing, rearing, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Affected SMHM may suffer from increased predation, competition, and reduced reproductive success. Proposed project activities may cause actively nursing mice nearby to abandon their nests leading to mortality of their pups.

Intolerable levels of disturbance may force individual SMHM to flush from cover and expose themselves to contact with construction personnel and equipment. SMHM that come into contact with construction personnel or equipment are at risk of being trampled or crushed which could result in injury or mortality. SMHM could also get injured or killed if they were to come in contact with vegetation clearing equipment.

The Army proposes to employ the flushing or hazing of mice to compel them to leave the Action Area before and during vegetation removal. The act of “flushing” mice could result in injury, mortality, or stressors to individual SMHM that could interfere with normal behaviors. The likelihood of injury or mortality would depend on several factors such as the experience of the biologist conducting the activity, the methods, and resiliency of the individual SMHM. Even if no injury occurred, active hazing may cause immediate or latent stressors that could result in future harm and reduced survivability to the individual SMHM. This may manifest in adverse behaviors such as not being able to find or seek adequate shelter which could expose them to predation or adversely affecting foraging, feeding or reproductive behaviors.

The proposed project will result in temporary impacts to 0.6 acre of habitat. The proposed project site is partially overgrown with marsh vegetation and may conceal SMHM. Therefore, vegetation will need to be cleared around the work areas to allow access by wheeled and tracked equipment. The Army proposes to allow the project area to return to pre-project conditions through the natural regrowth of vegetation.

The Army proposes to implement several conservation measures for the SMHM which include preconstruction surveys, a Service-approved biologist on site during activities such as vegetation removal, and worker awareness training. These measures reduce, but do not eliminate the potential for adverse effects to the SMHM and may not be sufficient to reduce construction noise, visual disturbance, or physical impacts in areas where SMHM are present.

Add Cumulative Effects:

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section; they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the

Service did not identify any future non-federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Update Conclusion for SMHM:

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species*, the *Environmental Baseline*, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Army's Reinitiation of Informal Consultation for the General Repair of the T-4/T-7 Bridges included in the General Bridges, Roads, and Utilities Project at Military Ocean Terminal Concord (MOTCO), Contra Costa County, California is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the SMHM. This is based on the current status and distribution of the SMHM's population range-wide as analyzed in the species' most recent 5-year reviews and additional recent population/distribution data available to the Service, the small scope and short duration of construction activities, the small temporary impact to habitat in a localized area, and the implementation of the *Conservation Measures* to minimize the adverse effects on individual SMHM and their habitats during construction activities.

Add:

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to wildlife by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavior patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavior patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement (ITS).

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Army so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Army has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Army (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Army must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(4)].

Add Amount or Extent of Take:*Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse*

In accordance with 50 CFR 402.14(i)(1)(i), a surrogate for individual animals may be used to express the amount or extent of anticipated incidental take in the ITS. Surrogates are used for this ITS because it is difficult to accurately quantify and monitor the amount or number of individuals that are expected to be incidentally taken as a result of the proposed action. The Service anticipates incidental take of SMHM will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy in tidal marsh habitats resulting in low detectability. Therefore, the Service anticipates that individual SMHM will be subject to incidental take in the form of harm of all SMHM within suitable wetland and upland habitats of the approximately 0.75-acre Action Area through the interference or impairment of essential behavior patterns which include breeding, feeding, or sheltering from the noise, vibration, and visual effects of project activities. Additionally, the Service anticipates injury and mortality to SMHM is likely to occur due to trampling, getting crushed under equipment, and exposure to predation. *Conservation Measures* proposed by the Army and described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* will reduce, but not eliminate, the potential for incidental taking of SMHM. Therefore, Service anticipates that no more than one (1) SMHM will be subject to incidental take in the form of injury and mortality within the Action Area. Upon implementation of the following *Reasonable and Prudent Measure*, take in the form of harm from impairing essential behaviors of SMHM and injury and mortality of one individual SMHM within the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Add Effect of the Take:

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that this level of anticipated take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the SMHM.

Add Reasonable and Prudent Measure:

The Service has determined that the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the Reinitiation of Informal Consultation for the General Repair of the T-4/T-7 Bridges included in the General Bridges, Roads, and Utilities Project at Military Ocean Terminal Concord (MOTCO), Contra Costa County, California on the species:

1. The Army shall minimize adverse effects to the SMHM to the fullest extent possible.

Add Term and Condition:

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Army shall comply with the following term and condition, which implements the Reasonable and Prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is nondiscretionary. The following Term and Condition implement the Reasonable and Prudent Measure:

1. The Army shall fully implement the proposed project, including the conservation measures, guidelines, implementing procedure, the Reasonable and Prudent Measure, and the corresponding Term and Condition as described in this biological opinion.

Add Reporting Requirements:

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Army shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Army must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Army shall follow the steps outlined in the *Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and CNDDDB (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/BIOS>).

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

Add:**REINITIATION—CLOSING STATEMENT**

This concludes formal, informal, and informal conference consultation on the Reinitiation of Informal Consultation for the General Repair of the T-4/T-7 Bridges included in the General Bridges, Roads, and Utilities Project at Military Ocean Terminal Concord (MOTCO), Contra Costa County, California. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16,

1. Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:
 - a. If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
 - b. If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;

- c. If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
 - d. If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.
2. An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:
- a. Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
 - b. Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Brian Hansen, Senior Fish and Wildlife Biologist, at Brian_Hansen@fws.gov or (916) 930-5642 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 2025-0134939-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

Add:**LITERATURE CITED**

(Service) U.S. Fish and Wildlife. 2013. Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California. Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California. xviii + 605 pp.
https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf

_____. 2021. 5-YEAR REVIEW: Salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*). San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California. 29 pp.
https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3630.pdf

WRA Environmental Consultants. 2022. Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse Survey Results Military Ocean Terminal Concord. Concord, Contra Costa County, California. October 2022.